

Adult Presentation of Intestinal Malrotation Complicated by Volvulus and Ladd's Band Obstruction: A Case Report of Missed Diagnosis

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Introduction

An embryological abnormality – a structural defect or malformation present at birth due to errors during embryonic development – could manifest in a variety of conditions, though the defect may not be apparent until adulthood. Malrotation occurs when the intestines fail to complete the normal 270-degree counterclockwise rotation and fixation during fetal development. It is usually diagnosed in childhood, but can also be found in adults incidentally or be present with an acute abdomen due to complications like cecal volvulus and Ladd band obstruction. Intestinal malrotation predisposing to midgut volvulus requires emergency surgery in which division of the Ladd's band is essential.

Case Presentation

We report a case of a 22-year-old male patient with a BMI of 13.4, who was referred to the Surgical Unit for upper bowel obstruction. He underwent emergency surgery at the referring hospital for an ileo-colic volvulus accompanied by ileal perforations and localised peritonitis, with the procedure involving ileo-colic resection, terminal ileostomy, and peritoneal lavage. Upon admission, he appeared cachectic, dehydrated, hypotensive, anaemic, and presented with coagulopathy and dyselectrolytemia due to frequent vomiting. CT scan revealed distended stomach and duodenum, while barium meal indicated intestinal malrotation with delayed duodenojejunal passage. He was reoperated on, and during the exploratory laparotomy, a tight, large fibrous Ladd's band compressing the duodenum was discovered and removed. Following this, he displayed good digestive tolerance and all deficits were compensated. After six months in significantly improved biological condition, he underwent elective surgery: restoration of bowel continuity through ileocolic anastomosis.

Conclusion

Adult intestinal malrotation complicated by volvulus and persistent Ladd's band obstruction is rare and may be overlooked due to nonspecific clinical presentation. Therefore, this case emphasizes the importance of recognizing congenital rotational anomalies in adults and adhering to the complete surgical principles of the Ladd procedure in order to prevent recurrent obstruction and reintervention.

Keywords

Intestinal malrotation; Midgut volvulus; Ladd's band